

Effects of Dutch agri-environmental field margins and bird plots on cropland birds

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ABSTRACT

Agri-environmental measures (AEMs) are the main instrument of the Common Agricultural Policy to protect farmland biodiversity, but their effectiveness is questioned. In the Netherlands, AEMs have been implemented by farmers' collectives since 2016, with the goal to improve the spatial targeting and coordination of measures, and thereby increase their effectiveness. The objective of this paper is to assess the effects of two AEMs, bird plots and field margins, on the abundance of seven cropland bird species targeted by the Dutch agri-environmental policy, and on their total abundance and species richness. The study was carried out in four farmers' collectives in the provinces of Groningen, Drenthe and Flevoland in the Netherlands. We assessed how bird abundance and species richness measured on AEM plots and control plots were related to management and landscape factors. Furthermore, we assessed whether bird abundance and species richness measured on AEM plots were related to the spatial concentration of other AEM plots in landscapes surrounding AEM plots. With regard to plot management, we found a significant positive effect of field margins on skylarks, yellowhammers, common linnets, common kestrels, total bird abundance and species richness. Bird plots had a significant positive effect on skylarks and total bird abundance. However, western yellow wagtails, northern lapwings and Eurasian oystercatchers did not benefit from the two studied measures, likely because the vegetation in the bird plots and field margins is too high and dense for these species. Landscape factors, such as landscape openness, had contrasting effects on the analysed species, due to their different habitat requirements. Hence, there are no optimal landscapes for all target species, which underlines the need for a fine scale spatial targeting of measures based on species habitat requirements. Furthermore, the spatial concentration of other AEM plots in the landscape surrounding AEM plots had a significant effect for only two species (yellowhammer and western yellow wagtail), and this effect was negative. Thus, our results suggest that - for the studied species and landscapes - the type of measures and landscape in which they are taken are more important than their spatial concentration.

1. Introduction

European farmland biodiversity has been declining for several decades, and farming intensification is considered as one of the main drivers of this decline (Donald et al., 2001, 2006). Farming intensification results in homogenisation of landscapes (Benton et al., 2003) and environmental pressures, such as nutrients and pesticides pollution (Matson et al., 1997), which affect farmland species habitats. Furthermore, loss of farmland biodiversity threatens essential ecosystem services upon which agricultural production depends (Dainese et al., 2019). To protect farmland habitats and biodiversity,

Agri-Environmental Measures (AEMs) have been implemented in the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) since 1992. In 2020, expenditures on AEMs amounted to about 2.5 billion euros, 17.6% of the total CAP expenses on rural development (European Commission, 2021). However, past reviews of AEMs effectiveness indicate ambivalent results (Kleijn et al., 2011; Batáry et al., 2015; Staggenborg and Anthes, 2022), because management prescriptions sometimes fail to ensure a suitable habitat for target species (Uthes and Matzdorf, 2013), or suitable habitat is created but not in sufficient quantity or at the right location (Baker et al., 2012). Furthermore, AEMs effectiveness is often modulated by the composition and structure of the surrounding landscape (Batáry et al., 2011; Schepers

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Fig. 1. location of sample plots (in red).

et al., 2013). Therefore, to be effective, AEMs should be tailored to the habitat requirements of species they target and the characteristics of landscapes where they are implemented (Batáry et al., 2015).

In this paper, we analyse whether AEMs targeting cropland birds in the Netherlands are effective in providing suitable breeding season habitat for target species. In the Netherlands, AEMs aim to protect 43 bird species which depend on four main farmland habitats: open grassland, open cropland, green (e.g. hedgerows) and blue landscape elements (e.g. ditches) (Anonymous, 2014). Besides these species conservation targets, AEMs are also expected to contribute to ecosystem services supporting agricultural production and nature inclusive farming (Erisman et al., 2017). However, past studies evaluating the effects of AEMs found no to limited effects on target bird species (Kleijn et al., 2001, 2004; Verhulst et al., 2006; Wiersma et al., 2014), and studies on the effects of AEMs on ecosystem services in the Netherlands are lacking (but see Mei et al., 2021). It was suggested that, to be effective, AEMs should be targeted on areas which offer the best potential for birds. For instance, AEMs that target meadow birds should be preferentially implemented in grasslands with a high groundwater level (Verhulst et al., 2006). Moreover, AEMs should be spatially and temporally coordinated in a mosaic management that offers sufficient shelter and food to birds at different stages of their life cycle (Oosterveld et al., 2010; Kuiper et al., 2013). Consequently, the Netherlands has adopted a collective approach for AEMs in 2016, to coordinate implementation of AEMs at the scale of landscapes rather than individual farms. In this collective approach, public authorities contract farmers' collectives to design, plan and implement AEMs schemes. In turn, farmers' collectives contract individual farmers to implement measures and provide technical guidance to ensure an appropriate location, management and coordination of measures (Terwan et al., 2016; Boonstra et al., 2021). Through this approach, it is expected that the

spatial targeting and coordination of measures will be improved, leading to an increased ecological effectiveness of the AEMs (Melman et al., 2016).

Recent evaluations (Boonstra et al., 2021; Klaassen et al., 2022) suggest that the spatial targeting has indeed improved with the collective approach. Public authorities and collectives have taken into account measured bird distributions to choose the locations of AEMs (Boonstra et al., 2021). In Groningen, this resulted in AEMs being located in areas with high cropland bird densities (Klaassen et al., 2022). With regards to spatial coordination, AEMs in cropland habitats tend to be more concentrated than before (Boonstra et al., 2021). However, the effect on bird abundance of such AEMs concentration has not yet been evaluated (Klaassen et al., 2022). Moreover, a comprehensive assessment of the ecological effects of the collective approach is still lacking. Klaassen et al. (2022) assessed the effects of AEMs on cropland birds in the province of Groningen in 2015 – 2020, using the provincial breeding bird census data (Wiersma et al., 2014; Sovon, 2022a), and concluded that the area of AEMs had only a weak effect on bird abundance, limited to a few species.

This study extends previous assessments on the effects of Dutch collective AEMs on cropland birds by analysing data from AEMs monitoring schemes in three provinces. Therefore, the objectives of this study are (1) to assess if AEMs in cropland areas provide a suitable habitat to target bird species, and (2) to assess the effect of AEMs spatial concentration on bird abundance. We compared cropland bird species abundance within AEMs plots and plots without AEMs (control plots) from four farmers' collectives in the time period 2017–2020. We assumed that a higher bird abundance in AEMs plots than in control plots indicated that AEMs were effective in enhancing bird habitat. However, differences in bird abundance and distribution between plots with and without AEMs may be confounded by the effect of landscape factors, due

Table 1
Number of study plots per collective, year and management type.

Collective	Plot management	Year				Total
		2017	2018	2019	2020	
AND	Bird Plot		1			1
	Field Margin		53	55	59	167
	Control		20	23	39	82
ANO	Bird Plot	15	14	22	21	72
	Field Margin	84	86	82	91	343
	Control	34	35	37	45	151
CMG	Bird Plot	6	9	17	16	48
	Field Margin	27	25	19	21	92
	Control	10	6	12	24	52
FAC	Bird Plot				14	14
	Field Margin				45	45
	Control				13	13
	Total	176	249	267	388	

to the fact that landscape composition and structure have an important effect on bird abundance in Dutch cropland areas (Kuiper, 2015; Teunissen and Melman, 2019; Klaassen et al., 2020, 2022). Therefore, we assessed how bird abundance is related to both management and landscape factors to disentangle management and landscape effects. Furthermore, we assessed the effects of the spatial concentration of AEMs in landscapes surrounding the AEM plots on bird abundance within the AEM plots. In the discussion, we draw implications from our results and provide recommendations for the selection, location and spatial coordination of AEMs. Moreover, we briefly discuss the agronomic benefits of the studied AEMs.

2. Methods

2.1. Case study areas and data

2.1.1. Case study areas and AEMs

AEMs in the Netherlands target four main habitat types: (1) open grassland, (2) open cropland, (3) green landscape elements (e.g. hedgerows) and (4) blue landscape elements (e.g. ditches). Each province has defined target areas of intervention for each type of habitat based on the current spatial distribution of target species. AEMs targeting cropland birds are implemented in winter to provide foraging grounds for species over-wintering in the country, and in spring to provide safe nesting sites and foraging grounds for breeding species. We focused on spring AEMs and 16 breeding cropland bird species targeted by the national policy (see Table A1 in Appendix for the list of species). We studied AEMs implemented by four collectives in East-Groningen (ANOG) in 2017–2020, Mid-Groningen (CMG) in 2017–2020, Drenthe (AND) in 2018–2020 and Flevoland (FAC) in 2020. Those collectives were selected because they had the required bird monitoring data for our study. There was no monitoring data available to assess winter AEMs.

Case study areas are located in the physio-geographical regions of marine clays (Flevoland, Mid- and East-Groningen) and high sandy soils (South-East Groningen, Drenthe) (see Fig. 1). Agriculture is the main land use (70–80% of the total land area) in the case study areas, with a mix of cropland and grassland. In Groningen and Drenthe, cropland represents about half of the cultivated area, and main crops are cereals, potato and sugar beet. Flevoland has a larger share of cropland (70%) and the main crop types also include field vegetables.

The main measures that target breeding cropland birds are so-called ‘bird plots’ (this study: mean area = 5.0 ha, range = 0.4–12.2 ha) and ‘field margins’ (this study: mean area = 1.7 ha, range = 0.07–11.2 ha). Bird plots and field margins are both managed to provide suitable breeding and foraging habitat. Bird plots are measures implemented on whole fields, where strips of a perennial fodder crop (red clover or alfalfa) alternate with flower strips, which consist of a mix of grasses,

grains and herbs (in Dutch, vogelakker, BoerenNatuur, 2021). The fodder crop covers about 70% of the field and can be mown up to three to four times per year (Schlaich et al., 2015). Prescriptions on the dates and frequency of mowing vary per collective. In Mid Groningen, a rest period of eight weeks is prescribed as soon as skylarks nests are detected. The first mowing usually takes place in the first half of June. In Drenthe, mowing is not allowed before July 15th and restricted to three mowing events with an interval of at least 45 days. In East Groningen, the first mowing usually takes place begin June (second or third year alfalfa crops) or in July (first year alfalfa crop). The interval between two mowing events is at least seven weeks in the summer but maybe reduced from September onwards. Field margins are 3–18 m wide and are sown with a mix of grasses, grains and herbs (in Dutch, kruidenrijke akker-randen, BoerenNatuur, 2021). Fields margins are in general established for two to three years. Recently, collectives implemented new whole field measures that consist of summer cereals sown at low density (in Dutch, vogelgraan, BoerenNatuur, 2021). However, the number of plots with this new measure was too low to be included in the analysis. We obtained georeferenced polygons for all implemented bird plots and field margins from SCAN-ICT, the geographic information system in which Dutch collectives register implemented AEMs (BoerenNatuur, 2022).

2.1.2. Bird monitoring data

Bird data was collected on 794 unique study plots, consisting of 87 bird plots, 418 field margins and 289 control plots. The control plots did not receive any management to provide suitable breeding and foraging habitat for cropland birds, and had a mean area of 2.6 ha (minimum: 0.04, maximum: 15.1). Main crop types of the control plots were cereals (34%), potato (21%) and sugar beet (15%), thus typical of the main crop types in the studied provinces. The control plots were selected by the collectives in the vicinity of AEM plots, so that their surroundings had similar characteristics to those of the AEM plots. Control plots that were too close (within bird species foraging ranges) to AEM plots were removed from the analysis (see Section 2.1.3). As 198 plots were counted in more than one year, we had in total 1080 observations (see Table 1): 135 bird plots observations, 647 field margins observations and 298 control plots observations. Our sample of AEM plots represented about 28% of all AEM plots (total number of AEM plots implemented by the collectives during the studied years was 2753).

Study plots were counted from three up to six times per breeding season, between April and July. We used the maximum of counts over the plot visits throughout the breeding season as indicator of birds abundance. Counting periods were selected to overlap with the breeding season of targeted species. Birds were counted by walking along plot edges and recording all birds observed inside the plot within a distance of 150 m. When a plot was more than 300 m wide, bird counters walked along an additional transect going through the middle of plots. Bird counters recorded species name, number of individuals counted and evidence of breeding or territorial behavior (see breeding codes in Table A2 in appendix). We refer the reader to Vogel et al. (2016) for a detailed description of the monitoring protocol. We included in our analysis all birds recorded in the plots, with or without evidence of breeding or territorial behavior (birds recorded as flying over the plots, breeding code 0, were excluded). Furthermore, to get insights in the specific use of plots as foraging or breeding habitats by species, we also analysed a subset of the data consisting of only bird observations with evidence of breeding or territorial behavior (excluding observations with breeding codes 1 – adult individual in possible breeding biotope and 3 – pair in suitable breeding biotope).

2.1.3. Landscape variables

We analysed the effects on bird abundance within the study plots of four categories of landscape variables: land cover, crop types, landscape structure and the spatial concentration of AEMs in the landscapes surrounding the plots (see Table 2). Landscape variables were calculated for

Table 2
Landscape variables.

Category	Variables	Description	Data source
Crop types	% alfalfa	% of landscape area	BRP 2017–2020
	% summer cereals		
	% maize		
	% rapeseed		
	% extensive grasslands		
	% Intensive grassland		
	% root crops		
	% extensive crops		
	% fallow land		
	% winter cereals		
Land cover	Crop diversity	Simpson Diversity Index	BRP 2017–2020
	% arable field margins	% of landscape area	ET map 2018
	% urban and other semi-built-up areas		
	% surface water		
	% hedges and tree lines		
	% forest		
	% coastal ecosystems		
Landscape structure	% nature terrain		
	% bogs and fens		
AEMs spatial concentration	Landscape openness	Visible area of the landscape from sightlines (in hectares)	Landscape Monitor, Wageningen Environmental Research, monitoring year: 2018.
	Mean field size	Mean field area in hectares	BRP 2017–2020
AEMs spatial concentration	% Field Margins	% of landscape area	SCAN-ICT
	% Bird Plots		

areas surrounding the study plots (including the study plots), at three scales (300 m, 500 m and 1000 m from the edge of study plots) which reflect the approximate foraging range or territory size of the studied species (see Table A1). We computed a buffer from the edge of study plots around each plot using the `st_buffer` function of the R package `sf` (Pebesma, 2018). Therefore, a plot landscape consisted of the plot itself and all other potential habitat areas located within birds approximate foraging range (CBS and Sovon, 2016) within which the landscape variables were quantified.

To calculate land cover and crop type variables, we used the ecosystem types (ET) map published by the Dutch Statistical Office (Statistics Netherlands and WUR, 2021) for the year 2018 and the crop type maps from the Dutch Agricultural Land Parcel Information System (BRP) published by the Netherlands Enterprise Agency (Ministerie van Economische Zaken Rijkdienst voor Ondernemend Nederland, 2022) for the years 2017, 2018, 2019 and 2020. The ecosystem type map distinguishes 50 ecosystem types, which are grouped in the three main categories (1) natural, (2) agricultural and (3) urban and other (semi-) built up areas. Agricultural ecosystem types are derived from the BRP, which identifies the cultivated crop on each parcel of the national agricultural area at the date of the 15th of May. However, the ET map was not available for the years 2017, 2019 and 2020 at the time of our study. Moreover, in the ET map, BRP crop types are aggregated and assigned to the dominant crop types in contiguous parcels. Therefore, we replaced the agricultural ecosystem types of the ET map with the original BRP data. New maps integrating natural and urban and other (semi-) built up areas from the ET map 2018 with crop types from the BRP data were produced for each year of the study (2017–2020). We considered the natural and urban and other (semi-) built up areas of the ET map 2018 as fixed over the period 2017–2020. The combined ET – BRP maps were produced with QGIS.

BRP crop types were aggregated in classes relevant to assess habitat suitability for cropland bird species, based on previous studies (Kragten et al., 2008; Wiersma et al., 2014; Kuiper, 2015; Teunissen and Melman, 2019; Klaassen et al., 2020, 2022; Visser et al., 2020). We also included crop diversity as variable, as it was found to be related to cropland birds abundance in past studies (Chamberlain et al., 2000; Chamberlain and Gregory, 2010; Ronnenberg et al., 2016). We selected the Simpson Diversity Index (SIDI) (Simpson, 1949) as crop diversity variable, as it is less sensitive to rare crop types and easier to interpret than the Shannon

Diversity Index (McGarigal, 2015). SIDI was computed with the function `diversity` of the R package `vegan` (Oksanen et al., 2013). Urban and other (semi-) built up areas ecosystem types were aggregated in one class ‘Urban and other (semi-) built up areas’. This class includes urban and rural built-up areas, infrastructures, public green spaces and other unpaved terrains in urban areas. Natural ecosystem types were aggregated in relevant classes for the study. For instance, all forest types were aggregated in one forest class, and all surface water types were aggregated in one surface water class. The surface water class did not include narrow (below 6 m width) linear water bodies such as ditches. We refer the reader to [Supplementary Materials](#) for complete details on the aggregation of crop types and ecosystem types.

We selected mean agricultural field size and landscape openness as landscape structure variables. Field size is associated with landscape homogeneity and related to farmland birds abundance and diversity (Noack et al., 2021; Šálek et al., 2021). Mean agricultural field size was calculated based on the BRP dataset. Some farmland bird species show preference for open landscapes (Rieger et al., 2021; Schmidt et al., 2022). Landscape openness was calculated from the 2018 landscape openness map produced by WENR with the model ViewScope (Meeuwssen and Jochem, 2015). The ViewScope model computes visible area of the landscape from sightlines (in ha) for 100-m pixels. The ViewScope model uses the same input data as the ET map: the national topographic map (Top10NL). A digital elevation model is added to take into account relief. We averaged the landscape openness map pixel values for each landscape surrounding study plots to obtain the landscape openness variable.

Variables of AEMs concentration in landscapes were calculated from geo-referenced polygons of implemented AEMs provided by the four collectives. We calculated the percentage of field margins area and the percentage of bird plots area in the total area within the buffers surrounding each study plot.

Landscape variables were computed in R with the packages `sf` (Pebesma, 2018), `raster` (Hijmans et al., 2015) and `exactextractr` (Baston et al., 2021).

After computation of landscape variables, we realized that a few control plots had AEMs plots within their landscape. We removed these control plots from the data, as bird abundance in these control plots may have been influenced by the proximity of AEMs. Moreover, landscapes of a few plots close to the German border were not completely covered

by the ET map and BRP data. We excluded from the analysis plots with less than 99% coverage. Tables A5 and A6 in the Appendix present the number of observations (unique plot-year combinations) that have been used in the statistical models for the three different landscape sizes (300 m, 500 m, 1000 m).

2.2. Statistical analysis

We developed statistical models for seven species: skylark (*Alauda arvensis*), western yellow wagtail (*Motacilla flava*), yellowhammer (*Emberiza citrinella*), common linnet (*Linaria cannabina*), common kestrel (*Falco tinnunculus*), northern lapwing (*Vanellus vanellus*) and Eurasian oystercatcher (*Haematopus ostralegus*). The nine other species could not be modeled (models did not converge), likely because they were recorded in too small numbers (see Tables A3 and A4). In addition to species analysis, we developed statistical models for total bird abundance and species richness (number of species considering only the 16 breeding cropland species targeted by the Dutch AEMs).

Control plots were selected so that they had no AEM in their landscapes (see Section 2.1.2). Therefore, plot management (control or AEM) was correlated with the area percentage of field margins and bird plots in the landscape. To avoid confusion between the effects of plot management and AEMs spatial concentration, we analysed these effects separately. To analyse the effects of plot management, we applied statistical models to the complete data set and did not include variables related to the spatial concentration of AEMs in landscapes (area percentage of field margins, area percentage of bird plots) in the models. As explained in Section 2.1.2, we applied the models to (1) all bird observations and (2) only bird observations with evidence of breeding or territorial behavior. To analyse the effects of the spatial concentration of AEMs in landscapes, we applied statistical models to a subset of the data including only AEM plots and tested whether the bird species abundances in AEM plots were related to the AEMs spatial concentration variables. This analysis was applied to all bird observations in plots. Overall, we developed 27 statistical models: 18 models to test plot management effects on the abundance of seven species, total bird abundance and species richness, and nine models to test the effects of AEMs spatial concentration on the abundance of seven species, total bird abundance and species richness within the AEMs plots.

For each of the 27 analysis, we fitted GLMMs with a logarithmic link and a Poisson (P), Generalized Poisson (GP) and Negative Binomial (NB) distribution. We carried out the models validation as described below and discarded models with validation problems (significant dispersion or zero-inflation test). When several models were acceptable, we used the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) to select the best model (P, GP or NB). In all models, we included region and year as random effects to control for regional physio-geographical characteristics, such as soil types (region), and yearly fluctuations of species populations (year). As 198 plots had been counted in more than one year, plot id was also included as random effect (nested in region) to account for the non-independence of repeated plot observations. Furthermore, landscape variables (see Table 2) were included as fixed effects to control for landscape factors. In the 18 models to test the effects of management, we added plot management (control, field margin, bird plot) as a fixed effect and applied the model to the complete dataset. In the nine models to test the effects of the spatial concentration of AEMs, we added the two AEMs spatial concentration variables (area percentages of field margins and bird plots in the landscape) as fixed effects and applied the model to a subset of the data including only AEM plots. In all models, differences in plot area were controlled by adding plot area as covariate (with a logarithmic transformation). An offset may also have been used to control for differences in plot area. However, when using an offset, one assumes that bird counts increase linearly with plot area (using plot areas as offset is equivalent to including log plot area as covariate with a coefficient fixed to 1). In our study, this was not the case, as directly shown by the outputs of our models: estimated coefficients of the

variable log plot area ranged from 0.25 to 1.31, and were close to 1 for only two models (See Tables A5 and A6). Therefore, we chose to control for differences in plot area by adding log plot area as covariate. Our approach aligns with Daskalova et al. (2019), who recommend to correct for plot size with a covariate rather than an offset in the absence of a linear relationship between bird abundance and plot area. All continuous covariates were standardized with the function MyStd in Zuur et al. (2009).

We expected collinearity issues due to correlation between landscape variables. For instance, landscape openness was correlated with the area percentage of urban and other semi-built up areas (300 m landscapes: -0.487 , p -value < 0.001) and the area percentage of winter cereals (300 m landscapes: 0.512 , p -value < 0.001). Correlation plots are presented in Supplementary Material. We checked collinearity using Variance Inflation Factors (VIF) after model fitting (generalized VIF were calculated for categorical variables), with a threshold value of 3 (Zuur et al., 2010). We successively removed the covariate with the highest VIF until all covariates had a VIF lower or equal to 3. Due to this covariate selection, the list of landscape covariates differed per model. We did not perform any other model selection. Presented models include all covariates retained after excluding covariates with a too high VIF.

For the yellowhammer models, we removed sample plots located in regions with marine clay soils, as the breeding areas of the yellowhammer are limited to the high sandy soil regions (Sovon, 2022b).

GLMMs were fitted with the R package glmmTMB (Magnusson et al., 2017). Model validation was carried out with the R package DHARMA (Hartig, 2017). We tested residuals uniformity, outliers, dispersion, zero inflation and plotted residuals against predicted values and covariates, both included and not included, in the model. We checked spatial correlation issues, with maps of residuals, residuals variograms (Pebesma et al., 2021) and tests with a Generalised Additive Model (GAM). We fitted a GAM with GLMMs residuals as response and the tensor product of plot latitude and longitude as smooth term. GAMs were fitted with the R package mgcv and the gamm function (Wood and Wood, 2015). In nearly all GAMs fitted to check spatial correlation, plot location was not significant (p -value > 0.05). There were two exceptions: (1) for residuals of the GLMM testing management effects on the Eurasian oystercatcher, plot location was significant (p -value = 0.038), but the adjusted R^2 of the model was 0.0173 and the explained deviance was 2.86% ; and (2) for residuals of the GLMM testing AEMs concentration effects on the common linnet, plot location was significant (p -value = 0.024), but the adjusted R^2 of the model was 0.0083 and the explained deviance was 1.21% . To check the robustness of these two GLMMs, we repeated the analysis with a spatial Generalised Additive Mixed Model (GAMM). We kept the same covariates as in the GLMMs but added the tensor product of plot latitude and longitude as smooth term to account for spatial auto-correlation. The spatial GAMMs coefficient values and significance levels were similar to those of the GLMMs.

We tested the significance of variables with a LR chi-square test (R drop1 function). To quantify the effects of plot management, we calculated estimated marginal means (EMMs) from the fitted GLMMs for control plots, field margins and bird plots, setting all other covariates at their mean. Therefore, estimated abundances of the three treatment factors were compared on an average plot, i.e. a plot having average size and landscape characteristics of all plots of the study. We assessed effects of management types through pairwise comparisons, with a 95% confidence level and the Bonferroni method for p -value adjustment. To visualize the effects of a particular landscape variable, we calculated EMMs when this landscape variable varies, keeping other covariates constant (set at their mean). We used the R packages emmeans (Lenth et al., 2019) and ggeffect (Lüdecke et al., 2020) for effect size quantification. We quantified effect sizes and generated graphs of landscape variables only for the models fitted to test management effects with all bird observations, because our goal was to quantify these effects for all birds using the plots, whether for breeding or foraging.

Fig. 2. Estimated regression coefficients (in the predictor scale) of management factors “bird plot” and “field margin” for each of the seven species, species richness and total bird abundance. B = species nesting in boundary features (hedges, ditches and trees), G = species nesting on the ground. A positive coefficient (point above the red line) means a positive relation with the response variable, a negative coefficient (point below the red line) means a negative relation with the response variable. Vertical bars correspond to 95% confidence intervals: when vertical bars cross the red line, the relationship is not significant at a 95% confidence level.

3. Results

We present only the outcomes of models fitted with all bird observations. Outcomes of models fitted with only bird observations with evidence of breeding or territorial behavior are presented in

Supplementary Material. The results of both analysis are very similar.

Complete model outputs are presented in Table A5 (management effect) and A6 (spatial concentration effect) in Appendix. Anova tables are presented in **Supplementary Material.**

3.1. Plot management effects

3.1.1. Effects on species

AEMs had a significant positive effect on the abundance of skylarks, yellowhammers, common linnets and common kestrels, but no significant effect on western yellow wagtails, northern lapwings and Eurasian oystercatchers. Considering all 16 target species together, AEMs had a significant positive effect on total bird abundance and species richness (see Fig. 2 and Table A5).

Strongest effects were found for skylarks, with positive significant effects of both bird plots (estimated regression coefficient = 0.96, p-value <0.001) and field margins (estimated regression coefficient = 0.56, p-value <0.001). Predicted skylark abundances in bird plots and field margins were respectively 2.6 (95% confidence interval: 1.7 – 4.1, p-value < 0.001) and 1.8 (95% confidence interval: 1.2 – 2.6, p-value < 0.01) times higher than in control plots (see Fig. 3).

Field margins had significant positive effects on the abundance of yellowhammers (estimated regression coefficient = 0.56, p-value <0.01), common linnets (estimated regression coefficient = 0.56, p-value <0.05) and common kestrels (estimated regression coefficient = 0.97, p-value <0.05). Predicted abundances were 1.7 (95% confidence interval: 1.1 – 2.7, p-value < 0.01), 1.7 (95% confidence interval: 1.0 – 3.0, p-value < 0.05) and 2.6 (95% confidence interval: 1.0 – 6.8, p-value < 0.05) times higher in field margins than in control plots, for yellowhammers, common linnets and common kestrels respectively. Contrary to field margins, bird plots did not have a significant effect on the abundance of common kestrels, yellowhammers and common linnets, even though they are expected to provide suitable foraging grounds for these species.

Fig. 3. Estimated Marginal Means (EMMs) of number of individuals per plot for each of the seven species and total bird abundance, and EMM of species richness per plot, for control plots, field margins and bird plots. B = species nesting in boundary features (hedges, ditches and trees), G = species nesting on the ground. Vertical bars correspond to 95% confidence intervals.

Table 3

Overview of landscape variables with a significant effect. + indicates a significant positive effect, - indicates a significant negative effect. * $p < 0.05$ ** $p < 0.01$ *** $p < 0.001$. ns indicates that no significant relationship was found. Empty cells indicate that the variable was not included in the model (too high VIF, see Section 2.2). Results from models with all bird observations. Only landscape variables with a significant effect in at least one of the models are shown. See Table A5 for the effects of all landscape variables.

	Response variables Landscape variables	Skylark (G)	Western yellow wagtail (G)	Northern lapwing (G)	Eurasian oystercatcher (G)	Yellowhammer (B)	Common linnet (B)	Common kestrel (B)	Species richness	Total bird abundance
Crop types	% summer cereals	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	+*	+**
	% intensive grasslands	ns	-*	+**		ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
	% fallow land	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	+*	ns	ns
Land cover	% root crops	ns	-*							
	% urban and (semi) built-up areas	-***	-***	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	-*	-*
	% hedges and tree lines	-*	-**	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	-**	-*
Landscape structure	% forest	-*	-***	-**	ns	ns	ns	ns	-***	-***
	Landscape openness	ns	ns			+	ns	ns	ns	+*
	Mean field size	+*	+*			ns	-**	ns	ns	ns

3.1.2. Effects on species richness and total bird abundance

Field margins had a significant positive effect on the species richness (estimated regression coefficient = 0.20, p -value < 0.01). Predicted species richness was 1.2 (95% confidence interval: 1 – 1.4, p -value < 0.01) times higher in field margins than in control plots. There was no significant effect of bird plots on species richness.

Both field margins (estimated regression coefficient = 0.26, p -value < 0.001) and bird plots (estimated regression coefficient = 0.25, p -value < 0.05) had a significant positive effect on total bird abundance. Predicted total abundance was 1.3 (95% confidence interval: 1.1 – 1.6, p -value < 0.01) times higher in field margins than in control plots, and 1.3 (95% confidence interval: 1.0 – 1.6, p -value < 0.05) times higher in bird plots than in control plots.

3.2. AEMs spatial concentration effects

The spatial concentration of AEMs, that is the area percentage of bird plots and field margins in landscapes surrounding AEMs, had a significant effect on the abundance of only two species: the western yellow wagtail and the yellowhammer. There was a significant negative effect of the area percentage of bird plots (estimated regression coefficient = -0.14 , p -value < 0.05) on the abundance of western yellow wagtail. There was a significant negative effect of the area percentage of field margins (estimated regression coefficient = -0.31 , p -value < 0.01) and the area percentage of bird plots (estimated regression coefficient = -0.22 , p -value < 0.05) on the abundance of yellowhammers. There was no significant effect of the area percentage of bird plots or field margins on species richness and total bird abundance. Models outputs are presented in Table A5 in Appendix.

3.3. Landscape effects

Table 3 presents the effects of landscape factors that had a significant relationship with the response variable in at least one of the models. Certain landscape variables were excluded from some of the models due to a too high VIF (> 3): the area percentage of winter cereals (excluded from the skylark, wagtail, linnet, lapwing, oystercatcher, species richness and total abundance models), the area percentage of root crops (excluded from the yellowhammer, linnet, kestrel, lapwing, oystercatcher, species richness and total abundance models), the area percentage of intensive grasslands (excluded from the oystercatcher model), landscape openness (excluded from the kestrel, lapwing and oystercatcher models) and mean field size (excluded from the lapwing

and oystercatcher models). When interpreting our results (see Discussion section), we discuss when excluded variables may have influenced the model outputs. Complete model outputs are presented in Table A5 and Figures A1 and A2 in Appendix.

3.3.1. Crop types

Few crop types were significantly related to response variables. Summer cereals and intensive grasslands were the only crop types with a significant effect in more than one model. Summer cereals had a positive relation with both species richness and total abundance, while intensive grasslands had a positive relation with Northern lapwings and a negative one with western yellow wagtails.

3.3.2. Land cover

Forest was the land cover with a significant effect in most models (see Fig. 4), followed by urban and (semi) built-up areas and hedges and tree lines. Those three variables depicting vertical structures in the landscape all had a negative effect when they were significantly related to response variables. That was the case for skylarks, western yellow wagtails, northern lapwings, Eurasian oystercatchers, species richness and total bird abundance. Conversely, the abundances of yellowhammers, common linnets and common kestrels were not significantly related to these vertical structures.

3.3.3. Landscape structure

Mean field size in the surrounding landscape had contrasting effects on bird abundance within the study plots: positive on skylarks and western yellow wagtails but negative on common linnets. Landscape openness had a positive effect on yellowhammers but surprisingly did not have any significant effect on other species, though it had a positive effect on total bird abundance.

4. Discussion

4.1. Plot management effects

In this study, we assessed the effectiveness of AEMs in providing good breeding season habitat for target cropland bird species. If AEM plots hold higher bird abundances than control plots, then it is likely that AEMs effectively enhance bird habitat. We did not have bird monitoring data to carry out a before after control impact (BACI) assessment. Therefore, our study design was susceptible to a self-selection bias (AEMs may be located preferentially in the fields that are already most

Fig. 4. effects of forest cover on EMMs of skylark abundance, western yellow wagtail abundance, northern lapwing abundance, species richness and total bird abundance. Shaded bands represent 95% confidence intervals. See Figs. A1 and A2 for other variables.

used by birds), as is often the case in AEM evaluation studies (Josefsson et al., 2020). In order to control for self-selection, our statistical models included the plot physio-geographical region as random effect and surrounding landscape characteristics as covariates. Therefore, variation in bird abundance related to favourable plot locations was attributed to the region or landscape covariates, and not to plot management. We did not expect a difference in habitat quality between AEMs plots and control plots due to management before 2016, because farmers usually rotate fields with AEMs after a few years in order to control weeds.

It should be noted that we did not assess the effect of AEMs on temporal changes in abundance (i.e. population trends) of the target species. A higher bird abundance in AEM plots compared to control plots may result from the redistribution of birds from unsuitable to suitable habitat patches, without any actual change in bird population. Moreover, positive effects of a suitable habitat during the breeding season may be reversed by other bottlenecks, such as a lack of food resources in winter or mortality during migration. Therefore, in the following discussion of our results and conclusion, the terms AEMs effect or effectiveness indicate the success or failure of AEMs in providing a suitable habitat to target species during the breeding season but cannot be interpreted as changes in species populations. Nevertheless, it seems reasonable to assume that enhanced habitat during the breeding season contributes positively to bird populations.

We found that AEMs had a positive effect on habitat provision for skylarks, yellowhammers, common linnets and common kestrels, species richness and total bird abundance, but no effect on Eurasian oystercatchers, northern lapwings and western yellow wagtails. Below we discuss the effects of field margins and bird plots per species.

4.1.1. Skylark

Both the field margins and bird plots had a positive effect on skylark abundance. This is in line with Kuiper et al. (2013), who showed that skylarks prefer field margins over other areas for foraging. Klaassen et al. (2022) also found a positive effect of field margins on skylark abundance. Bird plots are also expected to be suitable nesting sites for skylarks (Schlaich et al., 2015). In particular, strips of perennial fodder crops, such as alfalfa, in bird plots should offer favorable nesting conditions (Kuiper et al., 2015), providing the mowing regime is adequate during the breeding period (01st April to 15th June). In Drenthe, this is ensured with a rest period until Mid-July. In Groningen, the first mowing usually takes place begin June, but a rest period of at least seven to eight weeks is applied to ensure enough time for skylarks to complete their breeding cycle. Our findings confirm the positive role of bird plots on skylarks. Klaassen et al. (2022) however did not find any effect of bird plots on this species in their study in Groningen, perhaps because their bird count method differed to ours. In particular, Klaassen et al. (2022) counted birds within 300-m radius circles around census points and assessed the effect on bird counts of the area of bird plots within these circles. With bird plots making up on average only 0.76% of the counted area (personal communication by P. Wiersma), most birds were counted outside of the AEMs, diluting effects that bird plots may have had locally.

4.1.2. Yellowhammer

We found a positive effect of field margins on the abundance of yellowhammers, in agreement with findings of Klaassen et al. (2022) for Groningen. Previous studies have shown that sown field margins provide suitable foraging habitat for yellowhammers (Davey et al., 2010; Burgess et al., 2015; McHugh et al., 2016). As a large part of yellowhammers stay all year round in the studied regions, winter AEMs may have played a role in the difference of abundance between field margins and control plots (field margins landscapes had a higher area percentage of winter AEMs than control plots landscapes).

Flower strips in bird plots could in principle also provide suitable foraging habitats to yellowhammers, but we did not find a significant relationship between bird plots and yellowhammer abundance. This

may be due to sample size, since there were only 23 bird plots in the sandy soil regions, or due to location, given that flower strips in bird plots are not located at the edge of fields and then are more likely to be further away from yellowhammer breeding sites and song perches (hedges and trees) than field margins. Moreover, flower strips in bird plots may develop a different vegetation composition and structure than field margins, which could also explain why yellowhammer abundance is related differently to these two AEMs.

4.1.3. Common linnet

We found a positive effect of field margins on the abundance of common linnets, but no effect of bird plots. Common linnets usually breed in hedges and shrubs (Kujawa et al., 2020), so it is likely that they use field margins as foraging grounds. Similar to the yellowhammer, the location and type of vegetation of flower strips may explain why bird plots did not have an effect on the common linnet.

4.1.4. Common kestrel

Field margins, but not bird plots, had a significant positive effect on the abundance of common kestrels. Field margins are expected to provide hunting grounds rich in voles for birds of prey (Broughton et al., 2014), and high densities of other birds (e.g. skylarks) in field margins may also attract common kestrels which prey on chicks. As in the case of yellowhammers, common kestrels stay all year round in the studied regions, thus the effect of field margins may be partly attributable to winter AEMs.

4.1.5. Western yellow wagtail

Western yellow wagtails did not benefit from any of the two studied AEMs. Western yellow wagtails are ground breeders and select breeding sites with a crop cover with not too dense vegetation. They often have nests in winter cereals (Kirby et al., 2012) and root crops late in the breeding season (Kragten, 2011). They forage on the ground often in open patches near ditches and tracks in fields where they breed (Gilroy et al., 2009). In principle, field margins could be suitable sites for foraging (Anonymous, 2014), as they are expected to provide an insect rich habitat. However, we found a (non significant) negative effect of field margins on western yellow wagtail abundance. This is probably due to an unfavorable vegetation height and structure in field margins, because the vegetation becomes too high and dense early in the breeding season.

4.1.6. Northern lapwing and Eurasian oystercatcher

The two studied AEMs did not support a higher abundance of northern lapwings and Eurasian oystercatchers than control plots. It is likely that the vegetation in bird plots and field margins is too high and dense for these two species. Indeed, Northern lapwings and Eurasian oystercatchers breed on bare or sparsely vegetated soil and are ground foragers, preying invertebrates on the soil surface and earthworms (Anonymous, 2014). Other types of AEMs are required for these species. Spring crops are favored sites for breeding (Bell and Calladine, 2017), but nests are vulnerable to agricultural operations and arable fields lack sufficient feed for chicks (Sheldon et al., 2004). Therefore, previous studies recommended to delay first agricultural operations or protect nests in spring crops in proximity to suitable foraging grounds for chicks, such as extensive grasslands (Sheldon et al., 2010; Horvat and Denac, 2019).

4.1.7. Species richness and total bird abundance

Bird plots did have a positive effect on total bird abundance but not on species richness. This reflects that bird plots are beneficial for a limited number of species, above all the skylark and possibly birds of prey (Schlaich et al., 2015), but there was no significant effect on the common kestrel and other birds of prey were hardly recorded in the sample plots (see Table A2).

Field margins did have a positive effect on total abundance and

species richness. Field margins benefited four of the seven studied species and may also have a positive effect on other species which could not be individually modelled, such as the grey partridge (*Perdix perdix*) and the Eurasian tree sparrow (*Passer montanus*) (Anonymous, 2014).

4.2. AEMs spatial concentration effects

The spatial concentration of AEMs in landscapes surrounding plots did not have any effect, except for yellowhammers and western yellow wagtails. Therefore, concentrating AEMs in the landscape does not seem to generally increase the effects of the measures: on average, an AEM plot with a relatively high concentration of other AEM plots in its landscape does not have a significantly different bird abundance or species richness than an AEM plot with a relatively low concentration of other AEM plots in its landscape, at least for the analysed species. We did not have bird abundance data for whole landscapes, thus we could not test whether increasing the area percentage of AEMs increases bird abundance and/or species richness at landscape scale. A positive effect at landscape scale seems likely in the case of skylarks, common linnets, common kestrels, total bird abundance and species richness: AEM plots have a higher abundance or species richness than other (control) plots and their effects do not decrease with spatial concentration. However, the relationship between the area percentage of field margins and yellowhammer abundance at landscape scale is ambiguous, because field margins have a higher abundance than other (control) plots but their effects decrease with spatial concentration.

The negative response of yellowhammers to the area percentage of field margins in plot landscapes may be related to the dataset used to fit the model. Plot landscapes in the yellowhammer model had a higher area percentage of field margins than plot landscapes in other models. Alternatively, our results could indicate that clusters of field margins provide too much foraging habitat to be used by yellowhammers breeding in their vicinity, pointing to a lack of suitable breeding sites (i. e. hedges and shrubs) close to field margins in our study areas. Other species are less sensitive to the availability of breeding sites close to field margins: skylarks may find suitable breeding sites in bird plots and nearby crops; common linnets and common kestrels have a larger foraging range than yellowhammers (see Table A1).

In this study, we limited our analysis to AEMs implemented in cropland habitats. However, several cropland species also depend on other types of habitats, such as open grasslands and green landscape elements. Therefore, we recommend future studies to assess the potential synergies between field margins and/or bird plots and other AEMs, such as delayed mowing of grasslands or the maintenance of hedgerows for bird abundance and species richness.

4.3. Landscape effects

The studied species differ in their preferences for landscape structure. On the one hand, skylarks, western yellow wagtails, northern lapwings and Eurasian oystercatchers prefer open landscapes (Gilroy et al., 2010; Anonymous, 2014), which was reflected in significant negative associations with the area percentage of urban and (semi) built-up areas, hedges and tree lines and forest in our study. On the other hand, yellowhammers, common linnets and common kestrels prefer half-open landscapes, where hedges and trees offer nesting sites, song perches and look out posts (McHugh et al., 2016; Kujawa et al., 2020). We did not find any significant association of these species with hedges and tree lines, though, probably because the small hedges and shrubs or isolated trees used by these species are not fully captured by the ET map (Grondard et al., 2021).

Mean field size in the surrounding landscape had a significant positive effect on skylark and western yellow wagtail abundance within plots but a significant negative effect on common linnet abundance within plots. Possibly, landscapes with small fields had a higher area percentage of small hedges and shrubs, which were detrimental to

skylarks and western yellow wagtails but benefited common linnets. However, the effect of mean field size may have been confounded with the effect of winter cereals (which was not included in these models), as the two variables were positively correlated (300 m landscapes: 0.437, $p < 0.001$, 500 m landscapes: 0.543, $p < 0.001$). Winter cereals fields are used by skylarks and wagtails for breeding (Gilroy et al., 2010; Hoffmann et al., 2018) and do not provide habitat to linnets (Kuiper, 2015).

Landscape openness was not significant in most models, probably because the variation in bird abundance linked to landscape openness was captured by other related covariates (the area percentages of urban and (semi) built-up areas, hedges and tree lines, and forest). In the lapwing model, the negative effect of forest is likely in part attributable to the exclusion of landscape openness, as the two variables were correlated (-0.44 , $p < 0.001$). Surprisingly, landscape openness had a significant positive effect on yellowhammers, but the data used for the yellowhammer excluded plots located in the clay soils regions (see Section 2.2), which are the most open ones. Therefore, our results are in line with the yellowhammer's preference for half-open landscapes.

Overall, species richness and total bird abundance were significantly negatively related to the area percentages of urban and (semi) built-up areas, hedges and tree lines, and forest. There was also a significant positive effect of landscape openness on total bird abundance. Those responses were driven by the prevalence of open landscape species, which represented 75% of all birds counted in the sample plots. Hence, our results should not be generalized to other regions, where species adapted to half-open and closed landscapes may be more abundant than in our study areas.

Effects of crop types were in general small and often not significant. This may in part result from collinearity between crop type variables. For instance, the effect of winter cereals, a crop preferred by western yellow wagtails for breeding (Gilroy et al., 2010), was not tested for this species because this variable was too strongly correlated with other variables to be included in the model. Moreover, certain species, such as the skylark and the western yellow wagtail, attempt multiple broods in different crop types (Kragten, 2011; Hoffmann et al., 2016). As our response variable was the maximum of bird counts over the breeding season, our models did not capture these seasonal changes, which may have masked species preferences for certain crop types.

4.4. Agronomic co-benefits of AEMs

Among the target cropland bird species, birds of prey play an important role in the dynamics of rodents populations, an important pest in the Dutch agricultural areas (Wymenga et al., 2016). According to studies in other regions of Europe, measures providing habitat to birds of prey, such as the common kestrel and the barn owl, can be effective for the biological control of voles (Paz Luna et al., 2020; Montoya et al., 2021). However, this potential role of AEMs has not yet been assessed in the Netherlands.

Besides explicit target species of the Dutch AEM policy, the two studied AEMs may also benefit other species groups, thereby enhancing the delivery of ecosystem services supporting agricultural productivity. In principle, perennial flower strips established in bird plots and field margins could provide a favorable habitat to pollinators and natural pest enemies (Scheper et al., 2017; Ganser et al., 2019). However, a specific management may be required to ensure that flower strips have the adequate vegetation composition and structure to actually provide these ecosystem services (Albrecht et al., 2020; Cole et al., 2020; Mei et al., 2021; Scheper et al., 2021; Image et al., 2022).

5. Conclusion

Our results show a higher abundance of four of the seven studied species, skylark, yellowhammer, common kestrel and common linnets,

on AEM plots compare to control plots. Therefore, it is likely that AEMs provide good breeding season habitat to these four species. However, while field margins had a higher abundance of these four species compare to control plots, the benefits of bird plots were limited to the skylark. None of the two measures benefited the western yellow wagtail, northern lapwing and Eurasian oystercatcher. It is likely that vegetation in AEMs is too high and dense for these three species. Vegetation composition or structure may also explain why field margins and bird plots have different effects on the yellowhammer and common linnets. However, the current monitoring of AEMs does not systematically include observations of habitat characteristics created by the prescribed management, such as the development of vegetation composition and structure over time or the distance of AEM plots to other habitat elements (e.g. landscape linear features) in nearby areas. We recommend including such indicators of habitat characteristics in the monitoring of AEMs to understand the contrasted effects of AEMs on targeted species and support the design of more effective management options.

Our study confirms that cropland bird species targeted by AEMs are related in different ways to landscape characteristics. Thus, it is unlikely that a given area in a collective could be favorable to all 16 cropland bird species targeted by the Dutch national policy. Therefore, local conservation efforts should prioritize the species for which local characteristics in terms of landscape openness, density of linear landscape elements and cropping patterns are already most beneficial. Such prioritization should involve the identification of a subset of target species and the selection of AEM options specifically suited to benefit these species within collectives' sub-regions with homogenous characteristics.

The spatial concentration of AEMs in landscapes around plots had an effect on bird abundance in the studied AEM plots for only two species, and this effect was negative for both species. These results suggest that the spatial targeting of AEMs (e.g. the location of bird plots in open landscapes for skylarks) and the spatial coordination of AEMs with other habitats elements in the landscape (e.g. the location of field margins close to shrubs where yellowhammers are breeding), are more important for AEMs effectiveness than achieving a high spatial concentration of bird plots or field margins.

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Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data Availability

The data that has been used is confidential.

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Appendix

See Appendix Tables A1, A2, A3, A4, A5, A6.

Table A1

Breeding cropland bird species targeted by AEMs in the Netherlands (1). Breeding periods and territory sizes/foraging ranges taken from CBS and Sovon (2016).

Species	Breeding period	Territory size/foraging range (meters)
Western yellow wagtail (<i>Motacilla flava</i>)	01 st June – 20 th July	300 m
Montagu's harrier (<i>Circus pygargus</i>)	01 st May – 15 th August	1000 m
Corn Bunting (<i>Emberiza calandra</i>)	15 th May – 20 th July	500 m
Common wood pigeon (<i>Columba palumbus</i>)	20 th April – 31 st July	300 m
Barn owl (<i>Tyto alba</i>)	01 st February – 31 st August	1000 m
Common linnet (<i>Linaria cannabina</i>)	25 th April – 20 th July	500 m
Corn crake (<i>Crex crex</i>)	20 th May – 31 st July	500 m
Northern lapwing (<i>Vanellus vanellus</i>)	01 st April – 10 th May	1000 m
Grey partridge (<i>Perdix perdix</i>)	15 th February – 20 th June	500 m
Eurasian tree sparrow (<i>Passer montanus</i>)	01 st April – 15 th June	200 m
Rook (<i>Corvus frugilegus</i>)	15 th March – 10 th May	500 m
Eurasian oystercatcher (<i>Haematopus ostralegus</i>)	30 th April – 10 th June	1000 m
Common kestrel (<i>Falco tinnunculus</i>)	01 st March – 15 th July	500 m
Skylark (<i>Alauda arvensis</i>)	01 st April – 15 th June	300 m
Short-eared owl (<i>Asio flammeus</i>)	30 th April – 20 th June	1000 m
Yellowhammer (<i>Emberiza citrinella</i>)	01 st April – 20 th July	300 m

(1) The yellow wagtail (*Motacilla flava flavissima*) is also a target sub-species but we excluded this sub-species from our analysis since breeding yellow wagtails are not observed in our study areas (Sovon, 2021).

Table A2

Breeding codes used to record evidence of breeding or territorial behaviour.

Breeding code	Description
0	Observation without indication of territorial behavior, outside breeding biotope (e.g. bird flying high over the plot)
1	Adult individual in possible breeding biotope
2	Singing or courting individual in suitable breeding biotope
3	Pair in suitable breeding biotope
4	Courting pair in suitable breeding biotope
6	Bird visiting a likely nest
7	Alarm signs or other behavior indicating the presence of a nest with chicks
9	Transport of nest materials, nest construction
10	Distraction behavior
11	Previously used nest or egg shells
12	Fledglings
13	Used nest with unknown content
14	Transport of food or stool
15	Nest with eggs
16	Nest with chicks

Table A3

Number of plots with bird presence per species and number of birds counted on sample plots, for all bird observations.

	Bird Plots		Control Plots		Field Margins		All plots	
	Number of plots with birds presence	Number of birds counted	Number of plots with birds presence	Number of birds counted	Number of plots with birds presence	Number of birds counted	Number of plots with birds presence	Number of birds counted
Western yellow wagtail	102	374	180	600	293	800	575	1774
Skylark	81	390	81	176	184	408	346	974
Yellowhammer	7	8	50	76	185	308	242	392
Common linnet	25	45	32	47	130	210	187	302
Northern lapwing	25	66	34	55	48	105	107	226
Common kestrel	24	32	9	9	50	56	83	97
Eurasian oystercatcher	18	48	22	35	27	34	67	117
Common wood pigeon	14	32	12	13	37	50	63	95
Eurasian tree sparrow	3	19	6	47	12	35	21	101
Grey partridge	0	0	2	2	13	19	15	21
Montagu's harrier	3	3	4	4	7	7	14	14
Corn crake	3	3	0	0	4	4	7	7
Rook	2	9	0	0	2	4	4	13
Corn bunting	0	0	0	0	2	2	2	2
Short-eared owl	0	0	1	1	1	1	2	2
Barn owl	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
All target species	122	1029	227	1065	487	2043	836	4137

Table A4

Number of plots with bird presence per species and number of birds counted on sample plots, only for bird observations with evidence of breeding or territorial behaviour.

	Bird Plots		Control Plots		Field Margins		All plots	
	Number of plots with birds presence	Number of birds counted	Number of plots with birds presence	Number of birds counted	Number of plots with birds presence	Number of birds counted	Number of plots with birds presence	Number of birds counted
Western yellow wagtail	91	311	173	550	267	703	531	1564
Skylark	79	367	79	171	178	384	336	922
Yellowhammer	6	7	45	61	161	249	212	317
Common linnet	15	24	19	21	103	151	137	196
Northern lapwing	22	40	24	36	38	81	84	157
Eurasian oystercatcher	12	19	14	19	11	13	37	51
Common wood pigeon	5	6	5	5	14	15	24	26
Common kestrel	3	7	3	3	11	12	17	22
Eurasian tree sparrow	0	0	2	2	9	26	11	28
Grey partridge	0	0	1	1	6	7	7	8
Corn crane	3	3	0	0	3	3	6	6
Montagu's harrier	0	0	0	0	2	2	2	2
Short-eared owl	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1
Rook	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Barn owl	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
All species	119	784	213	869	444	1647	776	3300

Table A5

Complete outputs of models fitted to test the effects of plot management, with all bird observations. Estimated coefficients are given in the predictor scale. The intercept relates to control plots.

	Skylark (G)	Western yellow wagtail (G)	Northern lapwing (G)	Eurasian oystercatcher (G)	Yellowhammer (B)	Common linnet (B)	Common kestrel (B)	Species richness	Total abundance
Intercept	-1.96 ***	-0.19 *	-3.02 ***	-3.94 ***	-1.19 ***	-1.90 ***	-3.81 ***	0.21 *	0.53 ***
Log plot area	0.63 ***	0.45 ***	1.24 ***	0.96 ***	0.25 ***	0.51 ***	0.82 ***	0.43 ***	0.60 ***
Plot management effects									
Management - Field margin	0.56 ***	-0.19	0.08	0.11	0.56 **	0.56 *	0.97 *	0.20 **	0.26 ***
Management - Bird plot	0.96 ***	-0.2	-0.01	-0.43	0.05	-0.08	0.86	0.11	0.25 *
Crop types effects									
% alfalfa	-0.09	-0.08	0.23	0.16	-0.16	0.01	-0.06	-0.04	-0.04
% summer cereals	0.04	0	-0.09	-0.31	0.01	0.1	-0.03	0.06 *	0.08 **
% maize	-0.03	-0.02	-0.01	-0.21	0.09	-0.09	-0.11	0.02	0.01
% rapeseed	-0.02	-0.06	0.03	0.01	0.02	0.09	0.1	0.01	0.01
% extensive grasslands	0.08	-0.02	-0.03	0.17	0.09	0.09	0	0.02	0.04
% Intensive grasslands	-0.07	-0.10 *	0.40 **		-0.11	0.13	0.07	0.01	0.03
% root crops	-0.04	-0.12 *							
% extensive crops	0.04	0.05	0.01	-0.67	0	-0.23	-0.05	-0.04	-0.01
% fallow land	0.03	-0.04	-0.05	-0.04	-0.05	-0.05	0.14 *	0	0.02
% winter cereals					-0.07		-0.32		
Crop diversity (SIDI)	0.01	0.06	-0.05	-0.2	-0.1	0.01	0.19	-0.03	-0.04
Land cover effects									
% arable field margins	-0.01	0.02	-0.06	-0.07	-0.05	-0.09	-0.14	-0.01	-0.03
% urban and built-up areas	-0.43 ***	-0.21 ***	-0.16	0.03	0.08	-0.06	-0.25	-0.08 *	-0.08 *
% surface water	-0.14	-0.03	-0.15	0.09	-0.03	0.07	0.01	0.02	0
% hedges and treelines	-0.23 *	-0.21 **	-0.09	-0.06	-0.07	-0.13	-0.04	-0.09 **	-0.09 *
% forest	-0.21 *	-0.33 ***	-1.02 **	-1.45	0	-0.17	-0.56	-0.13 ***	-0.17 ***
% coastal ecosystems			0.02	0.08					
% nature terrain			-0.01	0.19					
% bogs and fens			0	-0.26					

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Table A5 (continued)

	Skylark (G)	Western yellow wagtail (G)	Northern lapwing (G)	Eurasian oystercatcher (G)	Yellowhammer (B)	Common linnet (B)	Common kestrel (B)	Species richness	Total abundance
Landscape structure effects									
Landscape openness	0.12	-0.04			0.24 **	0.06		0.03	0.10 *
Mean field size	0.16 *	0.09 *			0	-0.35 **	-0.29	-0.04	-0.02
Landscape size	300 m	300 m	1000 m	1000 m	300 m	500 m	500 m	500 m	500 m
Model type	NB GLMM	P GLMM	NB GLMM	NB GLMM	P GLMM	GP GLMM	P GLMM	GP GLMM	NB GLMM
Random Effects									
σ^2	1.62	0.83	2.47	3.13	1.16	2.28	2.56	0.43	0.51
τ_{00} plotid:region	0.22	0.29	0	0	0.05	0	0	0.02	0.08
τ_{00} region	0.3	0	0.64	0.75	0.05	0.15	0	0.02	0.04
τ_{00} year	0.03	0	0.06	0.02	0.01	0.03	0	0	0
ICC	0.25				0.09				
N plotid	758	758	623	623	399	725	725	725	725
N region	5	5	5	5	2	5	5	5	5
N year	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
Observations	1038	1038	900	900	562	1005	1005	1005	1005
Marginal R ² / Conditional R ²	0.384 / 0.539	0.388 / NA	0.578 / NA	0.566 / NA	0.159 / 0.231	0.178 / NA	0.361 / NA	0.351 / NA	0.489 / NA

* p < 0.05 ** p < 0.01 *** p < 0.001

Table A6

Complete outputs of models fitted to test the effects of AEM spatial concentration. Estimated coefficients are given in the predictor scale. The intercept relates to control plots.

	Skylark (G)	Western yellow wagtail (G)	Northern lapwing (G)	Eurasian oystercatcher (G)	Yellowhammer (B)	Common linnet (B)	Common kestrel (B)	Species richness	Total abundance
Intercept	-1.34 ***	-0.42 ***	-2.95 ***	-3.75 ***	-0.64 ***	-1.49 ***	-2.86 ***	0.38 ***	0.76 ***
Log plot area	0.71 ***	0.52 ***	1.31 ***	0.82 ***	0.38 ***	0.35 ***	0.95 ***	0.44 ***	0.64 ***
AEM clustering effects									
% field margins	-0.06	-0.11	-0.23	-0.01	-0.31 **	0.17	0.01	0.01	-0.04
% bird plots	0.1	-0.14 *	-0.35	0.05	-0.22 *	-0.03	-0.22	-0.05	-0.05
Crop types effects									
% alfalfa	-0.11	-0.16 *	0.13	0.15	-0.13	-0.09	-0.08	-0.08 *	-0.09 *
% summer cereals	0	-0.04		-0.39	0	0.11	-0.06	0.07 **	0.10 **
% maize	-0.08	-0.07	-0.03	-0.25	0.05	-0.18	-0.17	-0.01	-0.03
% rapeseed	-0.02	-0.13 **	0.01	-0.03	0.03	0.02	0.1	0	0
% extensive grasslands	0.06	-0.07	-0.18		0	0.11	0	0	0.02
% intensive grassland	-0.11	-0.13 *	0.43 **		-0.08	0.1	0	0.02	0.05
% root crops	-0.12	-0.19 **							
% extensive crops	0.01	0.05	0.04	-0.6	0.01	-0.26	-0.08	-0.06 *	-0.02
% fallow land	0.04	-0.01	-0.01	0.04	-0.05	-0.05	0.17 *	0.01	0.03
% winter cereals					-0.09		-0.3		
Crop diversity (SIDI)	-0.05	0.07	0.01	-0.27	0.03	0.03	0.09	-0.01	-0.03
Land cover effects									
% arable field margins	0.03	0.06	0.05	0.04	0.01	-0.06	-0.15	0	0
% urban and built-up areas	-0.49 ***	-0.26 ***	-0.36	-0.33	-0.01	-0.08	-0.23	-0.07 *	-0.12 *
% surface water	-0.11	-0.02	-0.07	0.1	-0.01	0.12	0.02	0.03	-0.01
% hedges and treelines	-0.1	-0.21 **	0.09	0.11	0.02	-0.14	-0.1	-0.08 *	-0.06
% forest	-0.2	-0.25 **	-0.86 *		-0.01	-0.11	-0.42	-0.16 ***	-0.16 ***
% coastal ecosystems			0.1	0.18					
% nature terrain			0.05	0.08					
% bogs and fens			-0.08	-0.36					
Landscape structure effects									
Landscape openness	0.11	0			0.24 **	-0.11		0.02	0.10 *
Mean field size	0.14 *	0.11 *			0	-0.1	-0.36		0.02
Landscape size	300 m	300 m	1000 m	1000 m	300 m	500 m	500 m	500 m	500 m
Model type	NB GLMM	P GLMM	NB GLMM	NB GLMM	P GLMM	GP GLMM	P GLMM	GP GLMM	NB GLMM
Random Effects									
σ^2	1.53	0.88	2.61	3.17	1.08	1.98	2.4	0.39	0.5

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Table A6 (continued)

	Skylark (G)	Western yellow wagtail (G)	Northern lapwing (G)	Eurasian oystercatcher (G)	Yellowhammer (B)	Common linnet (B)	Common kestrel (B)	Species richness	Total abundance
τ_{00} plotid:region	0.17	0.31	0	0	0.01	0	0	0.03	0.08
τ_{00} region	0.31	0	0.28	0.7	0.03	0.06	0	0.01	0.03
τ_{00} year	0.02	0	0.12	0.16	0	0.12	0	0	0
ICC	0.24								
N plotid	501	501	497	497	254	500	500	500	500
N region	5	5	5	5	2	5	5	5	5
N year	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
Observations	776	776	772	772	415	775	775	775	775
Marginal R ² / Conditional R ²	0.406 / 0.552	0.389 / NA	0.517 / NA	0.354 / NA	0.173 / NA	0.155 / NA	0.331 / NA	0.384 / NA	0.509 / NA

* p < 0.05 ** p < 0.01 *** p < 0.001

See Appendix Figs A1 and A2.

Fig. A1. effects of landscape variables on EMMS of abundance of skylarks, western yellow wagtails, northern lapwings, yellowhammers and common linnets. Shaded bands represent 95% confidence intervals. Only variables with p-value < 0.01 in each model are shown.

Fig. A2. effects of landscape variables on EMMS of species richness and total abundance. Shaded bands represent 95% confidence intervals. Only variables with p -value < 0.01 in each model are shown.

Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.agee.2023.108430](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2023.108430).

References

- Albrecht, M., Kleijn, D., Williams, N.M., Tschumi, M., Blaauw, B.R., Bommarco, R., Campbell, A.J., Dainese, M., Drummond, F.A., Entling, M.H., Ganser, D., Arjen de Groot, G., Goulson, D., Grab, H., Hamilton, H., Herzog, F., Isaacs, R., Jacot, K., Jeanneret, P., Jonsson, M., Knop, E., Kremen, C., Landis, D.A., Loeb, G.M., Marini, L., Mc Kerchar, M., Morandin, L., Pfister, S.C., Potts, S.G., Rundlof, M., Sardinias, H., Sciligo, A., Thies, C., Tschamrtke, T., Venturini, E., Veromann, E., Vollhardt, I.M.G., Wackers, F., Ward, K., Wilby, A., Woltz, M., Wratten, S., Sutter, L., 2020. The effectiveness of flower strips and hedgerows on pest control, pollination services and crop yield: a quantitative synthesis. *Ecol. Lett.* 23, 1488–1498.
- Anonymous, 2014. Soortenrijks Agrarisch Natuur en Landschapsbeheer - ANLB 2016.
- Baker, D.J., Freeman, S.N., Grice, P.V., Siriwardena, G.M., 2012. Landscape-scale responses of birds to agri-environment management: a test of the English Environmental Stewardship. *Scheme J. Appl. Ecol.* 49, 871–882.
- Baston, D., ISciences, L., Baston, M.D., 2021. Package ‘exactextract’. R Foundation for Statistical Computing. URL: <https://cran.r-project.org>.
- Batary, P., Baldi, A., Kleijn, D., Tschamrtke, T., 2011. Landscape-moderated biodiversity effects of agri-environmental management: a meta-analysis. *Proc. Biol. Sci.* 278, 1894–1902.
- Batáry, P., Dicks, L.V., Kleijn, D., Sutherland, W.J., 2015. The role of agri-environment schemes in conservation and environmental management. *Conserv. Biol.* 29, 1006–1016.
- Bell, M.V., Calladine, J., 2017. The decline of a population of farmland breeding waders: a twenty-five-year case study. *Bird. Study* 64, 264–273.
- Benton, T.G., Vickery, J.A., Wilson, J.D., 2003. Farmland biodiversity: is habitat heterogeneity the key? *Trends Ecol. Evol.* 18, 182–188.
- BoerenNatuur, 2021. Overzicht Beheerpakketten Agrarisch Natuur en Landschapsbeheer 2022. Beheerjaar 2022. BoerenNatuur, Utrecht.
- BoerenNatuur, 2022. SCAN-ICT. <https://www.boerenatuur.nl/wat-doen-we/scan-ict/22/12/2022>.
- Boonstra, F.G., Nieuwenhuizen, W., Visser, T., Mattijssen, T., Zee, F.F., v.d., Smidt, R.A., Polman, N., Boonstra, F.G., Nieuwenhuizen, W., Visser, T., Mattijssen, T., Zee, F.F., v.d., Smidt, R.A., Polman, N., 2021. Collective approach in progress: interim evaluation of the agri-environment scheme in the Netherlands. Wageningen. *Environ. Res.*, Wagening.
- Broughton, R.K., Shore, R.F., Heard, M.S., Amy, S.R., Meek, W.R., Redhead, J.W., Turk, A., Pywell, R.F., 2014. Agri-environment scheme enhances small mammal diversity and abundance at the farm-scale. *Agric., Ecosyst. Environ.* 192, 122–129.
- Burgess, M.D., Bright, J.A., Morris, A.J., Field, R.H., Grice, P.V., Cooke, A.I., Peach, W., 2015. Influence of agri-environment scheme options on territory settlement by yellowhammer (*Emberiza citrinella*) and corn bunting (*Emberiza calandra*). *J. Ornithol.* 156, 153–163.
- CBS, Sovon, 2016. Handleiding Sovon broedvogelonderzoek. PDF 2: Handmatige registratie en interpretatie van BMP-resultaten.
- Chamberlain, D.E., Gregory, R.D., 2010. Coarse and fine scale habitat associations of breeding Skylarks *Alauda arvensis* in the UK. *Bird. Study* 46, 34–47.
- Chamberlain, D.E., Vickery, J., Gough, S., 2000. Spatial and temporal distribution of breeding skylarks *Alauda arvensis* in relation to crop type in periods of population increase and decrease. *ARDEA-Wagening*. 88, 61–73.
- Cole, L.J., Kleijn, D., Dicks, L.V., Stout, J.C., Potts, S.G., Albrecht, M., Balzan, M.V., Bartomeus, I., Bebeli, P.J., Bevk, D., Biesmeijer, J.C., Chlebo, R., Dautarte, A., Emmanouil, N., Hartfield, C., Holland, J.M., Holzschuh, A., Knoben, N.T.J., Kovacs-Hostyanszki, A., Mandelik, Y., Panou, H., Paxton, R.J., Petanidou, T., Pinheiro de Carvalho, M.A.A., Rundlof, M., Sarthou, J.P., Stavrinos, M.C., Suso, M.J., Szentgyorgyi, H., Vaissiere, B.E., Varnava, A., Vila, M., Zemeckis, R., Scheper, J., 2020. A critical analysis of the potential for EU Common Agricultural Policy measures to support wild pollinators on farmland. *J. Appl. Ecol.* 57, 681–694.
- Dainese, M., Martin, E.A., Aizen, M.A., Albrecht, M., Bartomeus, I., Bommarco, R., Carvalho, L.G., Chaplin-Kramer, R., Gagic, V., Garibaldi, L.A., Ghazoul, J., Grab, H., Jonsson, M., Karp, D.S., Kennedy, C.M., Kleijn, D., Kremen, C., Landis, D.A., Letourneau, D.K., Marini, L., Poveda, K., Rader, R., Smith, H.G., Tschamrtke, T., Andersson, G.K.S., Badenhausser, I., Baensch, S., Bezerra, A.D.M., Bianchi, F., Boreux, V., Bretagnolle, V., Caballero-Lopez, B., Cavigliasso, P., Cetkovic, A., Chacoff, N.P., Classen, A., Cusser, S., da Silva, E.S.F.D., de Groot, G.A., Dudenhofer, J.H., Ekroos, J., Fijen, T., Franck, P., Freitas, B.M., Garratt, M.P.D., Gratton, C., Hipolito, J., Holzschuh, A., Hunt, L., Iverson, A.L., Jha, S., Keasar, T., Kim, T.N., Kishinevsky, M., Klatt, B.K., Klein, A.M., Krewenka, K.M., Krishnan, S., Larsen, A.E., Lavigne, C., Liere, H., Maas, B., Mallinger, R.E., Martinez Pachon, E., Martinez-Salinas, A., Meehan, T.D., Mitchell, M.G.E., Molina, G.A.R., Nesper, M., Nilsson, L., O'Rourke, M.E., Peters, M.K., Plecas, M., Potts, S.G., Ramos, D.L., Rosenheim, J.A., Rundlof, M., Rusch, A., Saez, A., Scheper, J., Schleuning, M., Schmack, J.M., Sciligo, A.R., Seymour, C., Stanley, D.A., Stewart, R., Stout, J.C., Sutter, L., Takada, M.B., Taki, H., Tamburini, G., Tschumi, M., Viana, B.F., Westphal, C., Willcox, B.K., Wratten, S.D., Yoshioka, A., Zaragoza-Trello, C., Zhang, W., Zou, Y., Steffan-Dewenter, I., 2019. A global synthesis reveals biodiversity-mediated benefits for crop production. *Sci. Adv.* 5 eaax0121.
- Daskalova, G.N., Phillimore, A.B., Bell, M., Maggs, H.E., Perkins, A.J., 2019. Population responses of farmland bird species to agri-environment schemes and land management options in Northeastern Scotland. *J. Appl. Ecol.* 56, 640–650.
- Davey, C.M., Vickery, J.A., Boatman, N.D., Chamberlain, D.E., Siriwardena, G.M., 2010. Entry Level Stewardship may enhance bird numbers in boundary habitats. *Bird. Study* 57, 415–420.
- Donald, P.F., Green, R., Heath, M., 2001. Agricultural intensification and the collapse of Europe's farmland bird populations. *Proc. R. Soc. Lond. Ser. B Biol. Sci.* 268, 25–29.
- Donald, P.F., Sanderson, P.J., Burfield, I.J., van Bommel, F.P.J., 2006. Further evidence of continent-wide impacts of agricultural intensification on European farmland birds, 1990–2000. *Agric. Ecosyst. Environ.* 116, 189–196.
- Erisman, J.W., Eekeren, Nv, Doorn, Av, Geertsema, W., Polman, N., 2017. Maatregelen Natuurinclusieve landbouw. Wageningen Environmental Research, Wageningen.
- European Commission, 2021. 14th Financial Report from the Commission to the European Parliament and the Council on the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD). 2020 financial year.
- Ganser, D., Knop, E., Albrecht, M., 2019. Sown wildflower strips as overwintering habitat for arthropods: effective measure or ecological trap? *Agric., Ecosyst. Environ.* 275, 123–131.
- Gilroy, J.J., Anderson, G.Q.A., Grice, P.V., Vickery, J.A., Watts, P.N., Sutherland, W.J., 2009. Foraging habitat selection, diet and nestling condition in Yellow Wagtails *Motacilla flava* breeding on arable farmland. *Bird. Study* 56, 221–232.
- Gilroy, J.J., Anderson, G.Q., Grice, P.V., Vickery, J.A., Sutherland, W.J., 2010. Mid-season shifts in the habitat associations of Yellow Wagtails *Motacilla flava* breeding in arable farmland. *Ibis* 152, 90–104.

- Grondard, N., Hein, L., Van Bussel, L.G.J., 2021. Ecosystem accounting to support the Common Agricultural Policy. *Ecol. Indic.* 131, 108157.
- Hartig, F., 2017. Package 'DHARMA'. R package.
- Hijmans, R.J., Van Etten, J., Cheng, J., Mattiuzzi, M., Sumner, M., Greenberg, J.A., Lamigueiro, O.P., Bevan, A., Racine, E.B., Shortridge, A., 2015. Package 'raster'. R. Package 734.
- Hoffmann, J., Wittchen, U., Stachow, U., Berger, G., 2016. Moving Window Abundance—a method to characterise the abundance dynamics of farmland birds: The example of Skylark (*Alauda arvensis*). *Ecol. Indic.* 60, 317–328.
- Hoffmann, J., Wittchen, U., Berger, G., Stachow, U., 2018. Moving window growth—a method to characterize the dynamic growth of crops in the context of bird abundance dynamics with the example of Skylark (*Alauda arvensis*). *Ecol. Evol.* 8, 8880–8893.
- Horvat, E., Denac, D., 2019. Population dynamics and habitat use by Northern Lapwing in agricultural landscape of Dravsko and Ptujsko polje (NE Slovenia). *Acrocephalus* 40, 3–22.
- Image, M., Gardner, E., Clough, Y., Smith, H.G., Baldock, K.C.R., Campbell, A., Garratt, M., Gillespie, M.A.K., Kunin, W.E., Mc Kerchar, M., Memmott, J., Potts, S.G., Senapati, D., Stone, G.N., Wackers, P., Westbury, D.B., Wilby, A., Oliver, T.H., Breeze, T.D., 2022. Does agri-environment scheme participation in England increase pollinator populations and crop pollination services? *Agric. Ecosyst. Environ.* 325, 107755.
- Josefsson, J., Hiron, M., Arlt, D., Auffret, A.G., Berg, Å., Chevalier, M., Glimskär, A., Hartman, G., Kačergytė, I., Klein, J., Knap, J., Laugen, A.T., Low, M., Paquet, M., Pasanen-Mortensen, M., Rosin, Z.M., Rubene, D., Žmihorski, M., Pärt, T., 2020. Improving scientific rigour in conservation evaluations and a plea deal for transparency on potential biases. *Conserv. Lett.* 13, e12726.
- Kirby, W.B., Anderson, G.Q.A., Grice, P.V., Soanes, L., Thompson, C., Peach, W.J., 2012. Breeding ecology of Yellow Wagtails *Motacilla flava* in an arable landscape dominated by autumn-sown crops. *Bird. Study* 59, 383–393.
- Klaassen, R., Wiersma, P., Visser, T., Sukkel, W., Prins, H., Melman, D., 2020. Scenariostudie Akkervogels - ecologische baten en financiële kosten van scenario's voor intensiever akkervogelbeheer. Rijksuniversiteit Groningen, Grauwe Kiekendief - Kenniscentrum Akkervogels, Wageningen University & Research, Groningen/Wageningen.
- Klaassen, R., Schultinga, M., Sirks, A., Kleyheeg, E., P, W., 2022. Evaluatie van de effecten van het agrarisch natuurbeheer op voorkomen en trends van akkervogels in de provincie Groningen 2015 - 2020. Grauwe Kiekendief - Kenniscentrum Akkervogels, Scheemda.
- Kleijn, D., Berendse, F., Smit, R., Gilissen, N., 2001. Agri-environment schemes do not effectively protect biodiversity in Dutch agricultural landscapes. *Nature* 413, 723–725.
- Kleijn, D., Berendse, F., Smit, R., Gilissen, N., Smit, J., Brak, B., Groeneveld, R., 2004. Ecological effectiveness of agri-environment schemes in different agricultural landscapes in The Netherlands. *Conserv. Biol.* 18, 775–786.
- Kleijn, D., Rundlof, M., Scheper, J., Smith, H.G., Tschamtké, T., 2011. Does conservation on farmland contribute to halting the biodiversity decline? *Trends Ecol. Evol.* 26, 474–481.
- Kragten, S., 2011. Shift in crop preference during the breeding season by Yellow Wagtails *Motacilla flava flava* on arable farms in The Netherlands. *J. Ornithol.* 152, 751–757.
- Kragten, S., Trimbos, K.B., de Snoo, G.R., 2008. Breeding skylarks (*Alauda arvensis*) on organic and conventional arable farms in The Netherlands. *Agric., Ecosyst. Environ.* 126, 163–167.
- Kuiper, M., Ottens, H., Van Ruijven, J., Koks, B., de Snoo, G., Berendse, F., 2015. Effects of breeding habitat and field margins on the reproductive performance of Skylarks (*Alauda arvensis*) on intensive farmland. *J. Ornithol.* 156, 557–568.
- Kuiper, M.W., 2015. The value of field margins for farmland birds. Wageningen University, Wageningen.
- Kuiper, M.W., Ottens, H.J., Cenin, L., Schaffers, A.P., van Ruijven, J., Koks, B.J., Berendse, F., de Snoo, G.R., 2013. Field margins as foraging habitat for skylarks (*Alauda arvensis*) in the breeding season. *Agric., Ecosyst. Environ.* 170, 10–15.
- Kujawa, K., Wuczyński, A., Dajdok, Z., Grzesiak, W., 2020. Effect of Habitat Structure and Crop Diversity on Common and Threatened Birds Breeding in Semi-Natural Field Margins. *Acta Ornithol.* 54, 181–199.
- Lenth, R., Singmann, H., Love, J., Buerkner, P., Herve, M., 2019. Package 'emmeans'. Lüdecke, D., Aust, F., Crawley, S., Ben-Shachar, M., 2020. Package 'ggeffects'. Create Tidy Data Frames of Marginal Effects for "ggplot" from Model Outputs 23.
- Magnusson, A., Skaug, H., Nielsen, A., Berg, C., Kristensen, K., Maechler, M., van Bentham, K., Bolker, B., Brooks, M., Brooks, M.M., 2017. Package 'glmmTMB'. R Package Version 0.2. 0.
- Matson, P.A., Parton, W.J., Power, A.G., Swift, M.J., 1997. Agricultural intensification and ecosystem properties. *Science* 277, 504–509.
- McGarigal, K., 2015. FRAGSTATS help. University of Massachusetts: Amherst, MA, USA, 182.
- McHugh, N.M., Goodwin, C.E.D., Hughes, S., Leather, S.R., Holland, J.M., 2016. Agri-Environment Scheme Habitat Preferences of Yellowhammer *Emberiza citrinella* on English Farmland. *Acta Ornithol.* 51, 199–209.
- Meeuwssen, H.A.M., Jochem, R., 2015. Openheid van het landschap: berekeningen met het model ViewScape. Wettelijke Onderzoekstaken Natuur & Milieu, Wageningen.
- Mei, Z., de Groot, G.A., Kleijn, D., Dimmers, W., van Gils, S., Lammertsma, D., van Kats, R., Scheper, J., 2021. Flower availability drives effects of wildflower strips on ground-dwelling natural enemies and crop yield. *Agric., Ecosyst. Environ.* 319, 107570.
- Melman, T.C.P., Schotman, A.G.M., Meeuwssen, H.A.M., Smidt, R.A., Vanmeulebrouk, B., Sierdsema, H., 2016. Ex-ante-evaluatie ANLB-2016 voor lerend beheer: een eerste blik op de omvang en ruimtelijke kwaliteit van het beheer in het nieuwe stelsel. Wageningen Environmental Research, Wageningen.
- Ministerie van Economische Zaken Rijkdienst voor Ondernemend Nederland, 2022. Basisregistratie Gewaspercelen (BRP). <https://data.overheid.nl/dataset/10674-basisregistratie-gewaspercelen-brp/#panel-description>. 22/12/2022.
- Montoya, A., Cabodevilla, X., Fargallo, J.A., Biescas, E., Mentaberre, G., Villanúa, D., 2021. Vertebrate diet of the common kestrel (*Falco tinnunculus*) and barn owl (*Tyto alba*) in rain-fed crops: implications to the pest control programs. *Eur. J. Wildl. Res.* 67, 79.
- Noack, F., Larsen, A., Kamp, J., Levers, C., 2021. A bird's eye view of farm size and biodiversity: the ecological legacy of the iron curtain. *Am. J. Agric. Econ.* 104, 1460–1484.
- Oksanen, J., Blanchet, F.G., Kindt, R., Legendre, P., Minchin, P.R., O'hara, R., Simpson, G.L., Solymos, P., Stevens, M.H.H., Wagner, H., 2013. Package 'vegan'. Community Ecol. Package, Version 2, 1–295.
- Oosterveld, E.B., Nijland, F., Musters, C.J.M., de Snoo, G.R., 2010. Effectiveness of spatial mosaic management for grassland breeding shorebirds. *J. Ornithol.* 152, 161–170.
- Paz Luna, A., Bintanel, H., Viñuela, J., Villanúa, D., 2020. Nest-boxes for raptors as a biological control system of vole pests: High local success with moderate negative consequences for non-target species. *Biol. Control* 146, 104267.
- Pebesma, E., 2018. Simple features for R: standardized support for spatial vector data. *R. J.* 10, 439–446.
- Pebesma, E., Graeler, B., Pebesma, M.E., 2021. Package 'gstat'.
- Rieger, M.R., Mailänder, S., Stier, L., Santon, M., Staggemorg, J., Anthes, N., 2021. Optimizing flower fields as an effective farmland eco-scheme also during non-breeding. *J. Appl. Ecol.* 59, 514–525.
- Ronnenberg, K., Strauß, E., Siebert, U., 2016. Crop diversity loss as primary cause of grey partridge and common pheasant decline in Lower Saxony, Germany. *BMC Ecol.* 16, 39.
- Šálek, M., Kalinová, K., Daňková, R., Grill, S., Žmihorski, M., 2021. Reduced diversity of farmland birds in homogenized agricultural landscape: A cross-border comparison over the former Iron Curtain. *Agric. Ecosyst. Environ.* 321, 107628.
- Scheper, J., Holzschuh, A., Kuussaari, M., Potts, S.G., Rundlof, M., Smith, H.G., Kleijn, D., 2013. Environmental factors driving the effectiveness of European agri-environmental measures in mitigating pollinator loss—a meta-analysis. *Ecol. Lett.* 16, 912–920.
- Scheper, J., Kleijn, D., de Groot, A., 2017. Bijvriendelijkheid van het Gemeenschappelijk Landbouwbeleid: een verkenning van de bijdrage van het huidige Gemeenschappelijk Landbouwbeleid aan het bevorderen van wilde bijen. Wageningen University.
- Scheper, J., Bukovinszky, T., Huigens, M.E., Kleijn, D., 2021. Attractiveness of sown wildflower strips to flower-visiting insects depends on seed mixture and establishment success. *Basic Appl. Ecol.* 56, 401–415.
- Schlaich, A.E., Klaassen, R.H.G., Bouten, W., Both, C., Koks, B.J., Martinez-Padilla, J., 2015. Testing a novel agri-environment scheme based on the ecology of the target species, Montagu's Harrier *Circus pygargus*. *Ibis* 157, 713–721.
- Schmidt, A., Fartmann, T., Kiehl, K., Kirmer, A., Tischew, S., 2022. Effects of perennial wildflower strips and landscape structure on birds in intensively farmed agricultural landscapes. *Basic Appl. Ecol.* 58, 15–25.
- Sheldon, R., Bolton, M., Gillings, S., Wilson, A., 2004. Conservation management of Lapwing *Vanellus vanellus* on lowland arable farmland in the UK. *Ibis* 146, 41–49.
- Sheldon, R.D., Chaney, K., Tyler, G.A., 2010. Factors affecting nest survival of Northern Lapwings *Vanellus vanellus* in arable farmland: an agri-environment scheme prescription can enhance nest survival. *Bird. Study* 54, 168–175.
- Simpson, E.H., 1949. Measurement of diversity. *nature* 163, 688–688.
- Sovon, 2021. Vogel Atlas. <https://www.vogelatlas.nl/>. 22/12/2022.
- Sovon, 2022a. Meetnet Agrarische Soorten (MAS). <https://www.sovon.nl/tellen/telprojecten/meetnet-agrarische-soorten-mas>. 22/12/2022.
- Sovon, 2022b. Vogelatlas - Numbers and distribution of breeding and wintering yellowhammers in The Netherlands. <https://www.vogelatlas.nl/atlas/soorten/soort/18570>. 22/12/2022.
- Staggemorg, J., Anthes, N., 2022. Long-term fallows rate best among agri-environment scheme effects on farmland birds—A meta-analysis. *Conserv. Lett.* 15, e12904.
- Statistics Netherlands, WUR, 2021. Natural Capital Accounting in the Netherlands - Technical report.
- Terwan, P., Deelen, J.G., Mulders, A., Peeters, E., 2016. The cooperative approach under the new Dutch agri-environment climate scheme. Background, procedures and legal and institutional implications. Ministry of Economic Affairs, The Hague, The Netherlands.
- Teunissen, W.A., Melman, T., 2019. Beheer van vogels in akkerland en kleinschalig cultuurland. *Vakbl. Nat. Bos Landsch.* 22–25.
- Uthes, S., Matzdorf, B., 2013. Studies on agri-environmental measures: a survey of the literature. *Environ. Manag.* 51, 251–266.
- Verhulst, J., Kleijn, D., Berendse, F., 2006. Direct and indirect effects of the most widely implemented Dutch. *Agric. -Environ. Schemes Breed. waders. J. Appl. Ecol.* 44, 70–80.
- Visser, T., Melman, D., Harmsel, Rmt, Maas, D., Sloothaak, J., Moonen, S., Buij, R., Bote, Ad, Visser, T., Melman, D., Harmsel, Rt, Maas, D., Sloothaak, J., Moonen, S., Buij, R., Bote, Ad, 2020. Systematiek classificeren habitatkwaliteit agrarisch gebied ten behoeve van het ANLB. Wageningen Environmental Research, Wageningen.
- Vogel, R., Wiersma, P., Roodbergen, M., Vlaanderen, O., 2016. Beheermonitoring van vogels in open akkerland in Oost-Groningen. Sovon Vogelonderzoek Nederland & Stichting Werkgroep Grauwe Kiekendief, Nijmegen, Scheemda.

- Wiersma, P., Ottens, H.J., Kuiper, M.W., Schlaich, A.E., Klaassen, R.H.G., Vlaanderen, O., Postma, M., Koks, B.J., 2014. Analyse effectiviteit van het akkervogelbeheer in provincie Groningen. Scheemda.
- Wood, S., Wood, M.S., 2015. Package 'mgcv'. R package version 1, 729.
- Wymenga, E., Latour, J., Beemster, N., Bos, D., Bosma, N., Haverkamp, J., Hendriks, R.F. A., Roerink, G.J., Kasper, G.J., Roelsma, J., Scholten, S., Wiersma, P., Zee, Evd, 2016. Terugkerende muizenplagen in Nederland: inventarisatie, sturende factoren en beheersing. Altenburg & Wymenga.
- Zuur, A.F., Ieno, E.N., Walker, N.J., Saveliev, A.A., Smith, G.M., 2009. Mixed effects models and extensions in ecology with R. Springer.
- Zuur, A.F., Ieno, E.N., Elphick, C.S., 2010. A protocol for data exploration to avoid common statistical problems. *Methods Ecol. Evol.* 1, 3–14.